

CONTACT FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF BISMALLEIMIDE POLYMER AND ITS COMPOSITE UNDER FRETTING CONDITIONS

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SUMMARY

Polymer matrix composites have drawn considerable interest in the mould processes. The vibrations and fatigue stresses induced in the moulds made evident to characterize the bismaleimide polymer and its composite HexTOOLTM under fretting conditions. Fretting is a small-amplitude oscillatory motion between contacting surfaces. The running conditions fretting maps (RCFM) of BMI resin and HexTOOLTM composite at temperature conditions were established. The influence of fretting regimes on the cracking propagation was shown. Under contact fatigue processes the crack nucleation and propagation of primary cracks at temperature conditions was studied. From analytical analyses the relationships between the development of cracks and their tensile-compressive stresses was established. The influence of fibres in composite on the matrix fatigue behaviour was shown and the wear resistance of composite and BMI resin was compared. According to results of dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), the viscoelastic properties of studied materials were obtained.

Keywords: Contact fatigue, fretting wear, fretting fatigue, DMA

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites are widely used in aerospace applications. They are often exposed to sever conditions involving a wide range of temperatures and vibrations. Polymer matrix composites have also drawn considerable interest in the mould processes. Nowadays, only steel based moulds ensure a good quality of composite manufacturing during the Resin Transfer Moulding or Autoclave Processes [1]. However the investigations of industry show that steel is very sensitive to the vibrations and fatigue stresses induced in the moulds that cause specific damage (wear, cracking) leading with time to its degradation. So, it is necessary an alternative material that will be able to improve the properties of mould. For this purpose the composite HexTOOLTM based on matrix bismaleimide reinforced by carbon fibres was developed. Thermoset bismaleimide (BMI) resins have evolved as important matrix materials for polymer composites because of their good processing characteristics, superior thermal

stability, excellent chemical resistance, good dimensional stability, lightweight material and fatigue resistance [2-4].

Since the vibrations and fatigue stresses can lead to serious fatigue life reduction in engineering components, fretting phenomenon has drawn considerable attention in terms of research and development of appropriate models. Fretting is defined as small amplitude oscillatory motions between two solid surfaces in contact [5]. Depending on loading conditions, material properties and environment, fretting can cause fretting wear induced by debris formation and debris ejection or fretting fatigue involving crack nucleation and crack propagation [6]. Numerous studies have shown that wear and cracking processes often coexist within the same contact and thus, the terms of fretting-wear and fretting-fatigue interact [7]. In order to show the complexities of fretting damage Vingsbo and Soderberg, Vincent and Berthier have developed the fretting maps [8, 9]. The fretting map approach has shown that the damage evolution strongly depends on the sliding regimes. Cracking is mainly occurred under partial and mixed fretting regimes whereas wear is observed for larger amplitudes under gross slip regime [7].

The primary aim of this work is to study the contact fatigue behaviour of bismaleimide resin under fretting conditions. Therefore, the following goals have been fixed: 1. study the dynamic mechanical properties of matrix and composite based on the bismaleimide resin for better understanding of cracking behaviour; 2. determine the sensitivity of the contact cracking behaviour to the temperature; 3. show the influence of sliding regimes on the cracking evolution; 4. determine the sensitivity of the bismaleimide resin to the fracture toughness; 5. compare the wear resistance of matrix and composite based on the bismaleimide resin.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. Test configuration

2.1.1. Dynamic mechanical analysis

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) is a technique which can provide a convenient and sensitive testing system for rapid determination of thermo-mechanical properties of polymers and polymer-based materials as a function of frequency and temperature. It allows the measurement of the viscoelastic properties: the elastic (storage) modulus, the loss (viscous) modulus and damping or the loss factor [10]. In this paper the dynamic mechanical analyzer was used for measuring the temperature-dependant elastic modulus and the loss factor, $\tan\delta=E''/E'$, but also indirectly the glass transition temperature (T_g) via the molecular relaxation of the thermosetting bismaleimide resin and composite. Dynamic testing was performed using DMA50 0.1dB Metravib on a 26mm x 4.1mm x 1.5mm rectangular bar in the tensile mode. The temperature ranged from -100°C to 350°C at a heating rate of 1.5°C/min under a flow of nitrogen. The frequencies applied were in a range of 1-40 Hz.

2.1.2. Fretting tests

To investigate oscillating fatigue phenomena, an electrodynamic shaker system NENE was used (Fig.1a). It works in a way that the normal force P is kept constant while a tangential force (Q) and displacement (δ) are varied. Thus the fretting loop Q - δ , as

shown in Fig 1b, can be drawn to extract quantitative variables, including the dissipated energy (E_d), (i.e. the area of the hysteresis), which is also related to the friction work dissipated per fretting cycle, the sliding amplitude (δ_0) (i.e. the remaining displacement when $Q=0$), the tangential force amplitude (Q^*) and the displacement amplitude (δ^*). Contact geometry like sphere/plan configuration was used to investigate the effect of contact fatigue behaviour. It consists of moving ball-bearing steel sphere (radius 22.22 mm) contacting a rectangular specimen ($4.1 \times 20 \times 25 \text{ mm}^3$) under a constant normal load (120N). During a test, constant but also variable displacement amplitude sequences were imposed. In all the tests to be described, the frequency of the tangential loading was $f=10\text{Hz}$. The tests were performed in a closed chamber applying constant 40-50% relative humidity and the temperatures of 20 and 90°C.

Fig.1. (a) Schema of the experimental setup; (b) Fretting log of one fretting cycle

2.2. Materials

The fretting tests and dynamic mechanical analysis were carried out using a bismaleimide resin HexPly® M61 and carbon fiber reinforced bismaleimide composite HexTOOL™ (Hexcel, France).

Bismaleimide resin (BMI) is heat resistant thermosetting polymer (up to 300°C), which is considered to be a potential material system for the next generation of moulds. The standard curing cycle for BMI resin is autoclave processes at 190°C for 4 hours, followed by freestanding post-cure out of autoclave at 220°C for 16 hours (ramp: 1°C/min).

The composite HexTOOL™ consists of bismaleimide resin that was made by lay up of prepreg plies each of that is composed of randomly dispersed fibre carbon bundles (8x 60mm) that can be considered as quasi isotropic in the plane. Their volume in composite is 60%. Its standard curing cycle is the same as for BMI resin.

During the fretting tests the resin BMI and HexTOOL were tested against ball-bearing steel (AISI 52100). The mechanical properties of this steel are reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of ball-bearing steel (AISI 52100)

E (GPa)	ν	R_m (MPa)	$R_{p0.2}$ (MPa)	HRC
210	0,3	2200	2000	60-67

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Dynamic mechanical analysis

The composite HexTOOL™ was cut in the direction of fretting test. The specimens were tested in the tensile/compression mode. The comparative temperature curves of storage modulus and loss factor ($\tan\delta$) for resin BMI and its composite at $f=10$ Hz are presented in fig. 2.

Fig.2. Viscoelastic behaviour of BMI resin and HexTOOL™ composite ($f=10$ Hz)

Here, the different damping peaks are the result of different molecular motions (relaxations) in the resin. In the temperature range three relaxations were observed. Since the composite HexTOOL™ is based on the same resin that studied in this paper, the damping peaks have the similar behavior. The double damping peak of BMI resin and the broad peak of composite that is occurred at higher temperature is linked to the α -relaxation that is associated to the glass transition. At this main relaxation mode the storage modulus decreases abruptly and the material loses completely this stiffness and serviceability. The double peak of BMI and broad peak of composite is due to not fully cured resin [11]. Only, the presence of fibers prevents to distinguish well this double peak. The lower temperature γ peak centered at -73 - -75°C at 10 Hz is due to localized short-range motions. Between γ - and α -relaxations another peak located in the 100-150°C range and called as β peak was appeared. It seems linked with structural relaxation or presence of water [11, 12]. From fig.2 it is shown that at the same frequency (10Hz) the loss factor ($\tan\delta$) of composite is lower and the elastic modulus is higher than the same characteristics of BMI due to its reinforcement by the fibers.

The obtained results that will be used in the fretting tests are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Viscoelastic properties of studied materials for fretting tests

	T, °C	20	90
BMI	E', GPa	3,52	2,94
	$\tan\delta$	0,02	0,026
HexTOOL	E', GPa	13,9	
	$\tan\delta$	0,011	

3.2. Analysis of the contact fatigue behavior of resin BMI under fretting conditions

As mentioned before, the damage evolutions strongly depend on the sliding regimes (partial slip or gross slip). The partial slip corresponds to crack nucleation and crack propagation whenever the gross slip is mainly to wear mechanisms: debris formations and debris ejection. As for the contact the partial slip is characterized by sticking and sliding zone whenever for gross slip only the sliding zone is present. The information regarding the contact conditions can be summarized in Running Conditions Fretting Maps (RCFM) [8, 9]. RCFM is a function of the normal load (P) and the displacement amplitude (δ^*). The evolution of the sliding regimes is also characterised by the fretting loop shape. If the fretting loop has a closed elliptic shape, it corresponds to partial slip regime (PSR). Contrary, if it is characterized by rectangular shape, it relates to gross slip regime (GSR). The transient regime is classically called the mixed fretting regime (MSR) that has not a stable fretting loop. Fig.3 illustrates the sliding regimes for BMI resin at 20°C and 90°C.

Fig.3. Running condition fretting maps at 20°C (—) and 90°C (---) (PSR – partial slip regime, MSR – mixed slip regime, GSR – gross slip regime);● -experimental points at 120N

It is shown that the temperature influences on the shift of sliding transition to higher amplitude displacements. The slight shift at 90°C was observed. It is explained by slightly decreasing of elastic modulus (fig.2).

3.2.1. Description of cracking processes in bismaleimide polymer

It was established that whatever the fretting regime and the temperature was applied the first damage in the polymer body was associated with the early nucleation and propagation of two separate surface cracks situated close to the edge of the contact and at two approximately symmetrical locations along the sliding direction (fig.4a). These cracks named as “primary cracks” propagate in progressive fatigue-like manner, perpendicularly to the sliding direction and are observed whatever the sliding condition. Then, secondary multi-microcracks are subsequently generated. Their behaviour (nucleation and propagation) and location depend on the sliding regime. Under partial slip regime they are located in the external sliding zone (fig.4b) whereas under gross slip regime they are spread over the whole contact. Under this regime the activation of

multi-microcracks in the contact domain favour the formation of a crack pattern inducing the particle detachment and the formation of third body (fig.4c).

Fig.4. SEM observation of cracking nucleation and propagation ($P=120N$): a) crack propagation of the primary cracks at the edges of the contact ($90^{\circ}C, \delta^*=\pm 100\mu m, 10^3$ cycles); b) propagation of secondary cracks at partial slip regime ($20^{\circ}C, \delta^*=\pm 30\mu m, 2 \cdot 10^3$ cycles); c) secondary cracks unfilled by the third body at gross slip regime ($20^{\circ}C, \delta^*=\pm 100\mu m, 2 \cdot 10^5$ cycles)

To understand the nature of cracking nucleation and propagation, the scheme of cracking evolution is plotted in figure 5.

Fig.5. Scheme of cracking evolution

It presents the schematic evolution of tangential force amplitude (Q^*) as a function of number of cycles. The failure mechanism strongly depends on the tangential force amplitude. Three successive domains can be observed as a function of the increase of

Q*: Domain (I) - a non degradation domain where no crack nucleation was detected due to small value of tangential force;

Domain (II) – a domain where the primary cracks initiate and propagate. The crack length is maximal when Q* reaches its maximum;

Domain (III) – a domain where the secondary multi-microcracks initiate and propagate. The crack length stabilizes because the tangential force amplitude reaches a constant value.

It was established that the temperature strongly influenced on the propagation of the primary cracks (fig.6a). For example, their size change from 1,9 mm at 20°C to 3,6 mm at 90°C for a $\pm 100\mu\text{m}$ displacement amplitude.

Fig.6.a) Measured crack lengths in a BMI polymer as a function of the number of cycles and the imposed displacement amplitude: \blacktriangle - $\delta^*=\pm 100\mu\text{m}$, \blacklozenge - $\delta^*=\pm 30\mu\text{m}$. b) Maximum tensile stress σ_{11} at the edge of the contact using Elastic Mindlin-Hamilton's formulation (black points for gross slip regime and white points for partial slip regime): \blacksquare - 10^4 cycles, \blacklozenge - $8 \cdot 10^4$ cycles

A simple described fatigue contact mechanics analysis showed that the observed cracks at the vicinity of the contact edge is essentially induced by the action of alternate tensile and compressive stresses oriented along the sliding direction [7]. The stress analysis based on the elastic Mindlin-Hamilton's formulation [13-14] takes into account the effect of temperature regarding the friction coefficient and the Young modulus. The assumption of an elastic contact response is justified by the low loss factor $\text{tg } \delta$ of BMI resin at ambient and 90°C (about 0,02 at 20°C and 0,026 at 90°C) (fig.2) and similar measured contact radius at 20°C and 90°C (0,8mm). For above-described experiments the calculated values of tensile stress σ_{11}^{max} are in the range of 70 – 139 MPa at ambient temperature and 60-169 MPa at 90°C. As shown in Fig.3 an increase of temperature induces an increase of the coefficient of friction. This promotes an extension of the partial slip domain but also an increase of the cyclic stresses σ_{11}^{max} (fig.6b). this can explain why at 90°C the crack lengths are longer than at ambient condition. Moreover, an increase of the temperature can also decrease the intrinsic fatigue properties of the resin.

To demonstrate the influence of temperature on the cracking process, the analysis of crack nucleation occurrence (N_i) has been carried out in the partial, mixed and gross slip fretting regimes for 20°C and 90°C (fig.7). For each studied condition several iterative tests have been done to bracket the fretting cycles inducing the crack nucleation condition (i.e. surface crack length $l_i = 0 \mu\text{m}$). This analysis has been done for a constant normal force $P=120\text{N}$. Fig.7a shows a sharp decrease of the crack nucleation endurance with the applied displacement amplitude in the partial and mixed slip regime follow by a stable evolution in the gross slip regime. This is consistent with the fact that the tangential force amplitude, which controls the contact stressing, increases with the displacement amplitude in partial and mixed slip regimes but stabilize in the gross slip regime. One important result is the fact that the temperature tends to decrease the crack nucleation endurance mainly in the MSR and GSR regime. However to discriminate the relative effect between contact loadings and fatigue properties it is necessary to perform a stress analysis. Fig. 7b plots the crack nucleation endurance versus the corresponding computed stresses. This analysis clearly demonstrates that temperature decreases the crack nucleation resistance whatever the fatigue domain (low and high cycle fatigue). Hence, the fatigue limit at 10^6 cycles is around $\sigma_{11}^{\text{max}}=83 \text{ MPa}$ at 20°C and reduced to $\sigma_{11}^{\text{max}}=72 \text{ MPa}$ at 90°C.

Fig.7. Number of cycles to crack initiation as a function of the displacement amplitude at 20°C and 90°C ($P=120\text{N}$, $l_i=0\mu\text{m}$) (a); Maximum tensile stress σ_{11} at the edge of the contact using the Elastic Mindlin-Hamilton's formulation as a function of number of cycles to crack nucleation at 20°C and 90°C (b)

3.2.2. Wear resistance comparison of matrix and composite HexTOOL based on the bismaleimide resin

It is proved that the mechanism of crack nucleation and propagation in polymer matrix composite is different from polymer [15]. The presence of fibres in composite, especially the chaotic orientation of fibre bundles in laminate as in the case of composite HexTOOLTM, prevents the investigation of nucleation and propagation of primary cracks in the composite matrix. The characterisation of microcracking in the composite is a topical interest in the field of advanced composite materials. During the fretting tests, the wear of composite HexTOOLTM is always accompanied by fracture of fibres and nucleation and propagation of microcracking (fig.8a). It was established that

the parallel orientation of fibres along the sliding direction decreased the wear kinetics and thus, improved the wear resistance of composite HexTOOL™ (fig.8b). Hence, the addition of fibres in the bismaleimide matrix makes it less sensible to the crack propagation and so, they improve its wear resistance properties. The wear volume of BMI resin decreased from $81 \cdot 10^7$ to $3 \cdot 10^7 \mu\text{m}^3$ in joining with fibres.

Fig.8. a) Microcracks propagation in composite HexTOOL™ (20°C, $\delta = \pm 50 \mu\text{m}$, 250N); b) Comparison of wear resistance between BMI resin and HexTOOL™ composite with parallel orientation of fibres along the sliding direction

4. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to examine the contact fatigue behaviour of bismaleimide resin and its composite HexTOOL™ under fretting and temperature conditions. Based on these results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. According to results of dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), the viscoelastic properties such as elastic modulus and the loss factor of BMI resin and HexTOOL™ composite depending on the temperature were obtained. The different damping peaks due to the result of different molecular motions (relaxations) in the resin were found. It was concluded that the $\text{tg}\delta$ of composite is lower and its elastic modulus is higher than the BMI resin properties due to reinforcement of composite by the fibers.
2. According to obtained Running Condition Fretting Maps, three fretting regimes for resin BMI at 20° and 90°C were identified. At 90°C the slight shift to higher amplitude displacements due to small decreasing of elastic modulus was observed.
3. It was confirmed that the main initial damage was related to the nucleation and growth of cracks named as primary cracks at the edge of the contact that were induced under the action of alternate tensile and compressive stresses oriented along the sliding direction. For different fretting regimes three successive domains associated with absence of damage, cracking nucleation and crack propagation of primary cracks have been identified at 20°C and 90°C that was justified by the Elastic Mindlin-Hamilton's formulation. It was found that at 90°C the tensile stresses are higher due to an increase of the coefficient of friction. Besides, it was demonstrated and quantified that temperature decreased the fatigue properties (crack nucleation) of the resin.

4. Depending on the fretting regimes two types of secondary multi-microcracks were established. Under partial slip regime the microcracks nucleate and propagate in the over the whole external sliding zone. Under gross slip regime they nucleate and propagate in all the contact domain.
5. It was proved that the mechanism of crack nucleation and propagation in polymer matrix composite HexTOOL™ was different from BMI resin. The presence of fibres in composite makes the bismaleimide matrix less sensible to the crack propagation and thus, they improve its wear resistance properties.

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